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TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING GRAPHIC ORGANIZERS

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Abstract. *Learning and teaching languages is one of the most crucial areas in human society. Language, as a means of communication, can be practically mastered in a natural environment (within the family, in society) or in an organized setting (in class). Knowledge of linguistic phenomena is studied theoretically. In our era of flourishing international relations, knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism (polyglossia), is gaining tremendous importance. "We have been preparing for today's topic for a long time. In our address to the parliament, we specifically emphasized strengthening the study of physics and foreign languages. In a rapidly changing world, we must be prepared for competition. To reinforce the foundation of the Third Renaissance, we need to intensify the study of foreign languages. No matter how challenging it may be, we must pay attention to this issue and give it special emphasis. Students studying in the Republic of Uzbekistan typically learn three languages," the Head of State noted.*

Keywords: *Knowledge, parliament, human achievements, intellectually mature*

Introduction

The reforms being implemented in our country's education system are based on a democratic education system, where the ideas put forward aim to build the spiritual and legal culture of the individual on the basis of all human achievements, to ensure the priority of national and universal values in shaping the education system, and to prepare well-rounded, mature personnel for society. As a result of positively addressing these tasks, an intellectually mature, morally harmonious, physically healthy individual with a broad and deep worldview - in other words, a well-rounded person - is formed.

The educational process implemented in educational institutions creates favorable conditions for students' formation as individuals and their intellectual and moral development. The teacher's actions in presenting the topic according to the following conditions create the necessary environment for students to acquire

theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and abilities. Specifically, when conveying the topic to learners during classes, it is necessary to define clear objectives, didactic conditions (the ability to select the optimal combination of educational forms, methods, and tools, ensuring their interconnectedness and harmony, organizing the learning process, and precisely determining the time required for knowledge acquisition), and to form qualities such as not limiting the topic to theoretical expression, but developing students' spiritual and moral qualities, fostering their personal growth, and creating a creative, productive atmosphere in the group.

Students, in turn, should comprehend the essence of the topic, develop an internal need and interest in acquiring theoretical knowledge and corresponding practical skills and abilities, apply them in practical activities while mastering the topic, complete assignments on time and with high quality, and reinforce the acquired theoretical knowledge through independent activity.

Methodology

In the modern age of computer technologies, reproductive methods and means of education are unable to fully absorb the rapidly increasing flow of information entering society. Therefore, the times themselves dictate the need to use modern pedagogical technologies that comprehensively support traditional education to accelerate, develop, and enhance the effectiveness of education.

Consequently, modern pedagogical technology is an educational measure and program that meets all the requirements and conditions of contemporary pedagogy.

In presenting the topic, the teacher is required to have an in-depth understanding of pedagogical and didactic knowledge, the ability to quickly assess the essence of emerging situations and find solutions to them, consider the age and psychological characteristics of students, and possess the skill to monitor and fairly evaluate students' learning activities.

The use of innovative technologies in teaching the subject is aimed at developing students' systematic creative thinking and their ability to express non-standard ideas and opinions in solving creative tasks. It is recommended to use graphic organizers in the educational process. In particular, it is advisable to use graphic organizers in foreign language teaching. Organizers consist of schemes, diagrams, graphs, and tables that facilitate students' independent activities.

Organizing learning using such tools as the "VENN" diagram and "T" schema for teaching analysis in foreign language learning; "Cluster" and "Cinquain" for working with concepts; and "KWL," "Insert," "AVV," and "PMI" for working with text and teaching thinking, creates convenience for students to learn a foreign language.

Results and discussion

The use of concept-based organizers can be implemented as follows. As an example, let's consider the "Cinquain" method. "Cinquain" means a five-line poem, and it is a convenient method for checking students' vocabulary. Let's take the word "book" as the main concept.

1. Concept (noun) - a book 2. Adjectives - interesting, beautiful 3. Verbs - reading, writing, present 4. Attitude (phrase) - book is our friend 5. Synonym - a teacher

In the process of applying this method, students use their memory to find adjectives, verbs, an attitude, and a synonym related to the given basic concept. This serves to enhance the students' thinking process and expand their vocabulary.

“Cluster” is a branching method that helps students learn a subject in depth. It teaches students to freely and organically connect concepts or specific thoughts related to the topic. This method serves to expand students' thinking skills while studying the topic. At the same time, it helps students reinforce, master, and generalize the material, as well as present their ideas in a schematic form. The use of graphic organizers in foreign language learning further develops students' memory, thinking, perception, and attention, increases vocabulary, and broadens their knowledge and worldview.

By using graphic organizers, teachers help students become proficient and effective communicators in a foreign language. As a result, through engaging and interactive learning, students develop language skills for effective communication while mastering foreign languages.

5. Synonym - a teacher

Conclusion

In the process of applying this method, students, using their memory, strive to find a quality, verb, attitude, and synonym to the given basic concept. This serves to enhance the students' thinking process, as well as their vocabulary.

“Cluster” is a method of branching, which helps students learn a subject in depth, as well as teaches students to branch concepts or specific thoughts related to the topic freely, openly, and organically. This method serves to expand the thinking skills of students during the study of the topic. At the same time, it teaches students to reinforce, master, generalize, and present their ideas in a schematic form. The use of graphic organizers in foreign language learning further develops students' memory, thinking, perception, and attention, increases vocabulary, and expands knowledge and worldview.

By using graphic organizers, teachers help students become proficient and effective communicators in a foreign language. As a result, through interesting and interactive learning, learners develop language skills for effective communication, as well as the perfect study of foreign languages.

Literature

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